

A review: carbon fiber reinforced composites for automotive

Carbon fiber has been used in automotive area to reduce part weight and improve performance. In the decade, various attempts to make carbon fiber from resources to save carbon footprints such as lignin. Carbon fiber reinforcement and thermosetting resins is among the most popular choice of impregnates to make SMC and has excellent properties instead. In addition, carbon fiber can also be chopped and compounded with thermoplastics such as PP, PLA etc to produce high thermal resistance composites use for automotive area.

The use of biological resources derived carbon fiber not only help reduce the dependence of advanced composites on the volatile cost of petroleum, and thereby helping to reduce the cost of composite materials for automotive, but also help achieve sustainability of green car. In this talk, carbon fiber in composites for automotive will be addressed and give us an overview of its development in recent years.